

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUSIKOYO****FIRST NAME: MUNOKO****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Researching the topic (EUCLID 2019, 2)
2. Basic steps in writing an essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 15-20)
4. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-33)
5. Italics and quotation marks (EUCLID 2019, 47)

ACA-401ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one focused on academic writing. The coursepack examined various elements in writing such as essay writing, plagiarism, literature review, some rules of thumb including styles in writing. The book also observed the difference between American and British English, Chicago manual of style crib sheet as well as the Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2019, III-V).

Specifically, the first part of the book focused on the different stages of writing an essay. It also addressed the importance of proper citation by giving credit to the source of information (EUCLID 2019, 5-13). The second part of the book analysed various styles of writing while exploring the American English against the British English. This section also covered the Chicago Manual Style (CMS) crib sheet with special reference being made to a “Turabian style.” Subsequently, an illustration was provided showing Latin abbreviations and expressions. The authors however recommended that it is best to write using “plain language” which is simple and direct (EUCLID 2019, 56). The instructions and sample correction paper provided insights on how to use header style, footnotes, and proper grammar.

2) **BASICS OF RESEARCH IN ESSAYS**

ACA-401D period one has been very enlightening. It however took me longer to do my assignment, than I had anticipated. This is because I realized that I needed to internalize and fully understand the coursepack to effectively respond to it.

A good quote from my native language is “a good leader, is a good follower.” It seems that this also applies in essay writing and especially when carrying out research. As the coursepack notes,

A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are vital to essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question.

This can sometimes be mistaken for servitude. While the ideas of the researchers can be similar, their different personalities and experiences will produce different results. One must therefore be humble and willing to learn, as well as build up from the work of others.

Writing Academic Essays

EUCLID (2019) start by stating that “*an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence*” (1). While I agree with this statement, I also wish to suggest that an academic essay can be used to not only persuade but also inform readers of an idea based on evidence (Whitaker 2010, 2). I have always thought of academic essays as “thought influencers,” in a way that the society can look up-to the academicians for guidance.

Writing in general has always been a big part of my personal and career life. Learning how to write academic essays is exciting especially to discover that essay writing is not a linear process. This means that I will work through the different stages several times during the writing (EUCLID 2019, 2). EUCLID (2019) also suggest that the author should write up the first draft and review it the following day. I believe this is very necessary since it gives you a fresh perspective into the writing. I often use this principle in my personal writing and in conversations. Additionally, when you take time to think through and process the message you wish to relay, it generates more impact and gives you the desired results.

a) Use of Apostrophe and Conjunctions

I noted that one strategy of taking a view seriously is to “argue against yourself” when you make a criticism (EUCLID 2019, 15). This demands for a very high level of emotional intelligence to allow one to be objective. It is intriguing to learn that I can argue against my own ideas and build up the integrity of it. One way that I usually do this is by asking myself, “does this idea inspire hope?” If my answer is no, then I analyze and find

out why. If it is yes, then I conceptualize it further. It is important that an idea inspires hope because I feel that hope can trigger productivity and development in a society.

While I am aware that there are various styles of writing, the course pack recommended simple and direct English. I however noted some grammatical errors in placing a comma before and (in conjunction) in a list of items. Also writing a word like “sentence’s meaning” can be a mouthful. A simpler version can read as, “the meaning of the sentence” (EUCLID 2019, 17-20). Starting a sentence with “and” can also be confusing, especially since it appears to be a continuation of the same thought. I therefore think it is best to avoid starting sentences with conjunctions, unless one is very certain and confident of their usage.

i) *Style Guide and Differences that Matter*

As I was reading through the course pack, I was wondering whether there was room for variations in writing. I think it is important to have a standard and universal style of writing. I, however, appreciate the flexibility to re-create new guides. I was therefore enlightening to discover that a freelance writer can continually develop styles of writing or guides as per the preference of their customer (EUCLID 2019, 35-37). Just like in any other business, where products and services are customized to suit the customer. Considering the current technological era that has created a global community, social media has proved that words can be created and shortened. This allows room for creativity, using politically correct language, ethno-elect, and use of various jargons.

Understanding that American English differs from British English is crucial. I believe throughout the course pack the goal is to encourage consistency and professionalism. Reading through the sample correction paper was very enlightening. I especially appreciate how EUCLID (2019) edited the grammar and provided alternative use of words. I found the write up to be simple and direct, but this also got me concerned. I have a had a mixture of American and British English in my past education, hence I find myself mixing up the two unconsciously. Having a clear guideline is very useful as I now have a reference point that will assist in adopting the preferred English (EUCLID 2019, 27).

ii) *Keep it Simple!*

Exposing new students to academic writing is very critical. As I read through the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), I was amazed at how much I overlooked some details while writing. Elements like abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics, quotation marks, footnotes among other things, give meaning and emotion to the writing. Quotation marks for example, can be used to represent spoken language (Whitaker 2010, 11). EUCLID (2019) however indicates that quotation marks should be used only in the following.

- *Place quotation marks around a word or phrase given in a special sense or purposefully misused" (Gibaldi 91). For example, The Population Council*

criticized the "outrageous" position of the Church on birth control. Chicago calls these "scare quotes."

- *Use quotation marks to enclose a translation of a non-English term in your text. Addis Ababa, the name of the capital of Ethiopia, is literally translated "new flower."*

The use of Latin abbreviations and expressions was a great eye-opener. It seems that the Latin expressions should only be used in informal writing and in referencing. It is best that one should use simple, plain language for formal writing. I however appreciate that one has an option of using the English version of the Latin expression or abbreviation. For example, instead of using "i.e." you can use "that is."

3) CONCLUSION

Ultimately, my understanding of this coursework is to gain deeper knowledge of academic writing. This includes expressing my ideas professionally and clearly in simple, plain language. This course pack has also given me insights on various styles of writing as well as allowed me to interrogate the book, ACA-401ACA-401D course-pack period one.

My initial appreciation of academic writing was very limited. I am more fascinated at the discovery that essay writing is not a linear process. I am also intrigued to learn that there is flexibility to develop new styles and guides for writing. This is just like in business where the trader can customize products and services to suit the preferred customer. Also, my concerns for use of proper American or British English have been settled. I therefore submit that using simple and plain language is important for formal writing.

ACA-401D period one has been enjoyable, though it took me longer than I had anticipated. To fully write a response paper, you need to internalize the book, and relate it to your life. The strategy for Euclid University to expose student to academic writing at an early stage is commendable. I think it sets the tone for the consecutive courses. It also allows the students to get in the frame of mind that is required to achieve academic excellence.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Whitaker, Anne. 2010. *Academic Writing Guide: A Step-by-Step Guide to Writing Academic Papers*. City University of Seattle.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.